

Screening rices for good panicle exertion

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We evaluated panicle exertion in 40 genotypes, including 4 commonly cultivated medium-duration rice varieties, during 1987 wet season (Jun-Sep). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications.

Three plants/replication were selected

randomly at the end of 50% flowering. Panicle exertion was measured as the distance between the place of emergence of the flag leaf to the base of the panicle.

The varieties studied showed highly significant differences in panicle exertion. Exserted panicle length varied from 1.60 to 10.95 cm, with a 40% coefficient of variation (see table). T414, 864, 916, 979, 1037, 2253, 2256, 2292, 2699, 2710, 2730, and 2869 had significantly better exertion.

These types could be used to develop male-sterile lines with well-exserted panicles for hybrid seed production. ■

Panicle exertion in different rice varieties.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1987 wet season.

Type	Variety	Origin	Mean exertion length (cm)
T23	Safeda	Central province	6.33
T414	Long grain, awned	Madurai	<u>7.76</u>
T864	Kesse-Koyoba (m)	West Africa (Gambia)	<u>9.75</u>
T916	V. Melonoceros Kore	Russia	<u>6.90</u>
T951	Matali	Punjab	2.18
T979	Ichabtsi	China	<u>9.27</u>
T1004	Sauchaotsi	China	6.14
T1037	III 14-8	China	<u>9.78</u>
T1403	Thavalaikannan	Malabar	4.01
T1418	Gudumaskathi	S. Canara	6.33
T1621	Dc. Sierrikone	Africa	5.92
T1651	Madaoliso	Brazil	1.71
T1745	Senkar	Udumalpet	5.83
T2253	Lati Amtoo Mohar (157)	Bombay	<u>7.15</u>
T2256	Banaspatri (Medium)	Lashkar (Gwalior)	<u>10.95</u>
T2292	Kalomashine	Kalitong, Assam	<u>10.55</u>
T2337	Nira	USA	3.65
T2402	CP15	CRRI, Cuttack	6.60
T2408	Cuttack 10 Aikoku	CRRI, Cuttack	4.94
T2436	China 62	China	5.52
T2613	Chungnung No. 4	China	5.71
T2669	Varylava Ali Combo	Madagascar	6.16
T2684	Tainan 1	Japonica - Taiwan	5.51
T2688	Kaohsiung 64	Japonica - Taiwan	5.18
T2690	Irradiated Taichung 65	Japonica - Taiwan	5.23
T2699	(CP231/3 *Bluebonnet)/PI215936	-	<u>9.50</u>
T2706	PI215936/CI9214	-	6.11
T2710	PI 215936/CI 9214	-	<u>9.50</u>
T2717	CI 9402 (CP231/Bluebonnet)	-	5.71
T2721	(PI 215936/CI9214)	-	4.78
T2729	CI9155/(C.50/Kh.27)	-	4.08
T2730	Hsinchu 50	Taiwan	<u>10.11</u>
T2811	Cuttack 45 (Ch.45/AC 1951)	Cuttack	4.43
T2842	14	E. Punjab	2.54
T2845	1206-17-21	Maharashtra	4.46
T2869	Takao	Taiwan	<u>7.00</u>
-	IR20	Philippines	4.18
-	Ponni	Malaysia	5.98
-	Co 43	Coimbatore	1.60
-	Co 44	Coimbatore	2.94
	Overall mean		6.05
		LSD	0.83
		CV = 40.31%	

^aUnderlined values a significantly better than overall mean. *F* test significant at 1% level.

Yield potential

Genetic studies on rice flag leaf weight and midrib and side vein thickness

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Thicker rice leaves have been found to have higher photosynthetic rates. Some studies have related photosynthetic rate to the diameter of the leaf vascular bundles.

We studied the heritability of specific flag leaf weight (SLW), midrib thickness (TMR), and side vein thickness (TSV) at heading in parental and F₂ populations of Guichao 2/82-856 and Conggui 226/82-856. Vein thickness was measured by micrometer. Flag leaf area (A) was measured as

$$A = 2/3L_1L_2 + 1/3L_3(L_1 - L_4)$$

where L₁ = leaf length, L₂ = leaf greatest width, L₃ = leaf basal width, and L₄ = leaf length from the widest part to the pointed end.

Variety 82-856 had very thick leaves (SLW = 10.027 mg/dm², TMR = 78.07 mm, TSV = 38.51 mm). Guichao 2 and Conggui 226 had thinner leaves (for Guichao 2, SLW = 6.03 mg/dm², TMR = 41.47 mm, TSV = 23.80 mm; for Conggui 226, SLW = 6.227 mg/dm², TMR = 45.70 mm, TSV = 23.89 mm).

Leaf heritability (*h*²) was calculated as

$$h^2 = \frac{WF_2 - 1/2(VP_1 + VP_2)}{VF_2} \times 100$$

All F₁ values for TMR, TSV, and SLW in both combinations were between the two parents (see figure). The F₂ distributions for SLW and TSV were continuous and almost abnormal in both combinations. Distributions for TMR were skewed, showing predominance of the lower segregants, in both combinations. Heritabilities were SLW > TMR > TSV. For Conggui 226/82-856, heritabilities were 78.63% for SLW, 62.06% for TMR, and 27.10% for TSV. For Guichao 2/82-856, heritabilities were

F₂ distribution of TMR, TSV, and SLW in the cross of Guichao 2/82-856F₂.

72.52% for SLW, 66.19% for TMR, and 33.84% for TSV.

This suggests that SLW and TSV had multigenic and additive actions and that

TMR was controlled by some major genes and a small number of dominant genes with cumulative and unequal effect. ■

Photoperiod sensitivity of traditional rice variety of Andamans

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Local rice variety C14-8 occupies more than 50% of the rice area in Andamans. We compared its photoperiod sensitivity

with the moderate photoperiod sensitivity of modern variety CR1009 at 12° N lat. and 92-94° E long. The crops were sown on the 10th d of each month for 1 yr.

CR1009 sown in Oct flowered in 100 d. When sown in Mar and Apr, it flowered in 130 d (Fig. 1). C14-8 sown in Nov flowered in 115 d. When sown in Dec, it flowered in 341 d, the difference being 226 d. The basic vegetative phase

1. Days to flowering of rice varieties sown in different months.

2. Variation in daylength and temperature during different months in Port Blair, India.

of CR1009 was about 65 d and that of C14-8 80 d. The photoperiod-sensitive phase was about 30 and 226 d, respectively.

The marked difference in flowering durations with month of sowing is attributed mainly to response to varying daylengths in different months (Fig. 2). Variation in days to flowering was caused by difference in vegetative lag phase only. The basic vegetative, reproductive, and ripening phases were constant in both varieties.

C14-8 is highly sensitive to slight variations in daylength, indicating strong photoperiod sensitivity. ■

Association of rice ratooning ability and vigor with grain yield

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We evaluated rice ratooning ability, vigor, and yield in 22 rice cultivars during 1987 wet season. The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. At harvest, the main crop was cut leaving a 15 cm culm. The stubble was irrigated 3 d after harvest and 40 kg N/ha applied 7 d after harvest.

Ratoon vigor was assessed as 1 = extra vigorous, 5 = intermediate or normal, 9 = very weak. A ratoon rating (RR) was calculated as

$$RR = (1 - [0.1 \text{ ratoon vigor}]^{\text{av number of ratoon tillers/plant}})$$